

Śrīrāga – An Overview

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Abstract

Śrīrāga is one of the traditional rāga-s which is mentioned in many ancient texts or lakṣaṇa grantha-s and is also prevalent today. In the present day, Śrīrāga is one of the five Ghana-rāga-s that are popularly known as the Ghana-rāga-pañcakam that includes Nāṭa, Gauḷa, Ārabhi, Varāḷi and Śrī. Several compositions by different composers are available today in this rāga which are also a part of the concert repertoire of the present day. Since this rāga is considered to be very auspicious, maṅgaḷa kṛti-s were composed in this rāga by different composers. This rāga also provides scope for manōdharmā aspects like rāga, tāna, nerval and svarakalpana. This paper aims at studying the historical evolution of the rāga-lakṣaṇa of Śrīrāga as mentioned in the lakṣaṇa-grantha-s written during the mēḷa period.

Keywords: Sriraga, Ghana raga, Raga, Text, Lakshana grantha, Raga Lakshana, Kharaharapriya

Introduction

In the present day, Śrīrāga is a janya of the 22nd mēḷakarta Kharaharapriya. Śrīrāga is an auḍava-sampūrṇa rāga which has a krama ārōha and vakra avarōha. Gāndhāra and dhaivata are absent in the ārōha while Śrīrāga includes all the seven svāra-s in the avarōha. The svarasthāna-s of Śrīrāga are ṣaḍja, catuśruti ṛṣabha, sādghāraṇa gāndhāra, śuddha madhyama, pañcama, catuśruti dhaivata and kaiśiki niṣāda. The ārōha and avarōha of Śrīrāga is as follows:

Ārōha - S R₂ M₁ P N₂ Ś

Śrīrāga was classified as a mēla as well as a rāga in the earlier texts while it was later classified as a janya rāga under the 22nd mēlakarta Kharaharapriya once the 72 mēlakarta scheme was formulated.

Historic evolution of the rāga lakṣaṇa of Śrīrāga

The texts written during the mēla period are taken up for study to trace the evolution in the rāga-lakṣaṇa of Śrīrāga. They are:

- Svaramēlakalānidhi of Rāmāmātya (1550 A.D.)
- Rāgatālacintāmaṇi of Pōlūri Gōvindakavi (1600-1700)
- Sadrāgacandrōdaya of Puṇḍarīkaviṭṭhala (1583-1589 A.D.)
- Rāgamañjari of Puṇḍarīkaviṭṭhala (1572-1578 A.D.)
- Rāgamāla of Puṇḍarīkaviṭṭhala (1576 A.D.)
- Rasakaumudi of Śrīkaṇṭha (1575 A.D.)
- Rāgavibōdha of Sōmanātha (1609 A.D.)
- Saṅgītasudha of Gōvindadīkṣita (1614 A.D.)
- Caturdaṇḍiprakāśika of Veṅkaṭamakhi (1620 A.D.)
- Saṅgītapārijāta of Ahōbala (17th century)
- Rāgatatvavibōdha of Śrīnivāsa (after 1650 A.D.)
- Hṛdayakautuka of Hṛdayanārāyaṇadēva (1667 A.D.)
- Hṛdayaprakāśa of Hṛdayanārāyaṇadēva (1667 A.D.)
- Rāgatarāṅgiṇi of Lōcanakavi (after 1667 A.D.)
- Rāgalakṣaṇamu of Śāhaji (1684-1711 A.D.)
- Rāgalakṣaṇam of Mudduvēṅkaṭamakhi (first quarter of the 18th century)
- Saṅgītasārāmṛta of Tulaja (1729-1735 A.D.)

- Saṅgraha-Cūḍāmaṇi of Gōvinda (1750-1800 A.D.)
- Saṅgītasārasaṅgrahamu of Tiruvēṅkaṭakavi (1800 A.D.)
- Mahābharatacūḍāmaṇi (18th – 19th century)
- Rāgalakṣaṇa (18th - 19th century)
- Saṅgīta-Sampradāya-Pradarśini of Subbarāma Dīkṣita (1904 A.D.)

Classification

Śrīrāga is described in the above mentioned lakṣaṇa-grantha-s as an auspicious or prosperous rāga which is to be sung in the evenings. Svaramēlakalānidhi, Rāgatālacintāmaṇi and Hṛdayakautuka mention that Śrīrāga is an Uttama or a superior rāga.

The texts Rāgalakṣaṇamu of Śāhaji, Rāgalakṣaṇam of Muḍdu Veṅkaṭamakhi and Saṅgīta-Sampradāya-Pradarśini of Subbarāma Dīkṣita classify Śrīrāga as Ghana under the Ghana-Naya-Dēśi classification of rāga-s.

Svaramēlakalānidhi of Rāmāmātya, Rāgatālacintāmaṇi of Pōlūri Gōvindakavi, Sadrāgacandrōdaya, Rāgamañjari and Rāgamāla of Puṇḍarīkaviṭṭhala, Rasakaumudi of Śrīkaṇṭha, Rāgavibōdha of Sōmanātha, Saṅgītasudha of Gōvindaīkṣita, Caturdaṇḍiprakāśika of Veṅkaṭamakhi, Rāgalakṣaṇamu of Śāhaji, Rāgalakṣaṇam of Muḍdu Veṅkaṭamakhi, Saṅgītasārāmṛta of Tulaja, Saṅgīta-Sampradāya-Pradarśini of Subbarāma Dīkṣita mention Śrīrāga as a mēḷa and as a rāga under the same mēḷa indicating that a mēḷa and a rāga are different from one another.

Hṛdaya-Kautuka of Hṛdayanārāyaṇadēva and Rāga-Taraṅgiṇi of Lōcanakavi list Śrīrāga under the Karṇāṭa samsthān which corresponds to the 28th mēḷa Harikāmbhōji of the present day.

Saṅgraha-Cūḍāmaṇi of Gōvinda mentions Śrīrāga as the 22nd mēḷa which corresponds to the 22nd mēḷakarta Kharaharapriya while classifying it under the 72 rāgāṅga rāga-s scheme. While describing Śrīrāga as a rāga, Gōvinda mentions it to be derived from the 22nd mēḷa Kharaharapriya.

Saṅgīta-Sāra-Saṅgrahamu of Tiruvēṅkaṭakavi, Mahābharatacūḍāmaṇi and Rāgalakṣaṇa of unknown authors also mention Śrīrāga to be derived from the 22nd mēḷa Kharaharapriya.

Svarasthāna-s

The svarasthāna-s of Śrīrāga have remained the same through time except the rāga description seen in a few lakṣaṇa-grantha-s. Beginning from the text Svaramēlakalānidhi of Rāmāmātya, the svarasthāna-s have been mentioned as śuddha ṣaḍja, pañcaśruti ṛṣabha, sādihāraṇa gāndhāra, śuddha madhyama, śuddha pañcama, pañcaśruti dhaivata and kaiśiki niṣāda. The same svarasthāna-s have been mentioned for Śrīrāga in Rāgatālacintāmaṇi of Pōlūri Gōvindakavi, Saṅgīta-Sudha of Gōvinda Dīkṣita and Saṅgīta-Sārāmṛta of Tulaja. The varieties of ṛṣabha and dhaivata have been mentioned as catuśruti in texts including Sadrāgacandrōdaya, Rasakaumudī, Caturdaṇḍi-prakāśika and Rāgalakṣaṇam of Muḍdu Veṅkaṭamakhi. Rāgavibōdha mentions the variety of ṛṣabha and dhaivata to be tīvra which might be equated to the catuśruti ṛṣabha and catuśruti dhaivata of present day's practice. This corresponds to the 28th mēḷa Harikāmbhōji of the present day.

Puṇḍarīkaviṭṭhala mentions the svarasthāna-s of this rāga by indicating their levels from the śuddha positions. Puṇḍarīkaviṭṭhala in Rāgamañjari mentions that dhaivata, ṛṣabha and niṣāda have their positions up by one step while gāndhāra is up by three positions which might be corresponded to the Harikāmbhōji mēḷa of the present day. In Rāgamāla, he mentions that ṛṣabha, gāndhāra, dhaivata and niṣāda have their positions up by one step which can be equated to the present day's 22nd mēḷa. This indicates that there might have been 2 versions of the same

rāga or the presence of 2 different Śrīrāga-s (Corresponding to the 22nd and 28th mēḷa-s of the present day).

Saṅgīta-Pārijāta of Ahōbala and Rāga-Tattva-Vibōdha of Śrīnivāsa mention the svarasthāna of gāndhāra to be tīvra in which case it can be equated to the 28th (Harikāmbhōji) mēḷa of the present day. This description seems similar to Puṇḍarīkaviṭṭhala's description seen in Rāgamañjari.

Later texts like Saṅgraha-Cūḍāmaṇi of Gōvinda, Saṅgīta-Sāra-Saṅgrahamu of Tiruvēṅkaṭakavi, Saṅgīta-Sampradāya-Pradarśini of Subbarāma Dīkṣita, Mahābharatacūḍāmaṇi and Rāgalakṣaṇa of unknown authors classify Śrīrāga under the 22nd mēḷa and mention the svarasthāna-s to be ṣaḍja, catuśruti ṛṣabha, sādharāṇa gāndhāra, śuddha madhyama, pañcama, catuśruti dhaivata and kaisiki niṣāda which corresponds to what is prevalent today.

The above-mentioned texts describe ṣaḍja to be the amśa, graha and nyāsa svāra of Śrīrāga while Rāgavibōdha mentions ṛṣabha to be the graha, amśa svāra and ṣaḍja to be the nyāsa svāra. Saṅgītapārijāta, Rāgatattvavibōdha and Hṛdayaparakāśa mention that ṛṣabha is the graha, amśa and nyāsa svāra. These texts also mention that alpa prayōga-s of gāndhāra and dhaivata are seen in Śrīrāga even if they are absent in the ārōha and avarōha.

Ārōha and Avarōha

The ārōha and avarōha of Śrīrāga are mentioned in Saṅgraha-Cūḍāmaṇi, Saṅgīta-Sāra-Saṅgrahamu, Mahābharatacūḍāmaṇi, Rāgalakṣaṇa and Saṅgīta-Sampradāya-Pradarśini as S R M P N Ś - Ś N P D N P M R G R S, which is similar to the present day's ārōha and avarōha of Śrīrāga.

The prayōga-s “m g r s” and “s n d p” are seen in the illustrative phrases seen in Saṅgītapārijāta of Ahōbala, Rāgatattvavibōdha of Śrīnivāsa, Hṛdayakautuka and Hṛdayaparakāśa

of Hṛdaya Nārāyaṇadēva. The prayōga “s n d” is seen in the illustrative phrases (Udgrāha-prayōga section) seen in Rāgalakṣaṇamu of Śāhaji and Saṅgītasārāmṛta of Tulaja. So, the vakra prayōga in the avarōha might have been a later development as most of the other lakṣaṇa-grantha-s do not mention the usage or presence of any vakra prayōga and just mention that seven svāra-s are present in the avarōha.

Saṅgīta-Sampradāya-Pradarśini of Subbarāma Dīkṣita mentions that “r g r s” and “p d n p” are viśēṣa-rañjana-prayōga-s (unique and attractive phrases) and jīva-svāra-prayōga-s. Subbarāma Dīkṣita also mentions that the prayōga “p d n p” is to be sung or played only once in the gīta prabandha or kīrtana-s as advised by the pūrvācārya-s.

Conclusion

Śrīrāga is an older rāga which is seen in the history of Karṇāṭaka-saṅgīta tradition and is also prevalent today. In the earlier days, Śrīrāga was considered to be an auspicious and prosperous rāga that could be sung in the evenings. Śrīrāga was classified as a Ghana rāga under the Ghana-Naya-Dēśi classification of rāga-s.

It was classified as both a mēḷa and a rāga under the same mēḷa while it was later classified under the 22nd mēḷa (Kharaharapriya) once the 72 mēḷakarta scheme was formulated. Two versions of Śrīrāga are to be seen in the earlier days, one which corresponds to the 22nd mēḷa (Kharaharapriya) and the other to the 28th mēḷa (Harikāmbhōji) of the present day.

References

1. Hema Ramanathan, Rāgalakṣaṇasaṅgraha: Collection of Rāga Descriptions from Treatises on Music of the Mēḷa Period with translation and notes, publisher N Ramanathan, Chennai, 2004.
2. Ed. A. N. Jani, Rasakaumudī (A work on Indian Music by Śrīkaṇṭha), Sangeeth Natak Akademi, New Delhi, 1959.

3. Ed. D. K. Joshi, Hṛdayakautukam of Hṛdayanārāyaṇadēva, Pub. Bhalchandra Sitaram Sukthakar, Bombay, 1918.
4. Ed. D. K. Joshi, Hṛdayaprakāśa of Hṛdayanārāyaṇadēva, Pub. Bhalchandra Sitaram Sukthakar, Bombay, 1918.
5. Ed. D. K. Joshi, Rāgalakṣaṇam, Pub. Bhalchandra Sitaram Sukthakar, Arya-Bhushan Press, Bombay, 1914.
6. Ed. D. K. Joshi, Rāgamañjarī of Puṇḍarīkaviṭṭhala, Pub. Bhalchandra Sitaram Sukthakar, Bombay, 1918.
7. Ed. D. K. Joshi, Rāgatarāṅgiṇi of Lōcana, Pub. Bhalchandra Sitaram Sukthakar, Bombay, 1918.
8. Ed. D. K. Joshi, Rāgatattvavibōdha of Śrīnivāsa, Pub. Bhalchandra Sitaram Sukthakar, Bombay, 1918.
9. Ed. G Subbaramayya, Saṅgīta Sāra Saṅgrahamu of Tiruveṅkaṭa Kavi, The Music Academy, Madras, 1940.
10. Ed. Ganesh Sharma, Sadrāgacandrōdaya of Puṇḍarīkaviṭṭhala, Pub. Bhalchandra Sitaram Sukthakar, Nirnaya-sagar Press, Bombay, 1912.
11. N. Krishna Veni, Rāgatālacintāmaṇi of Pōḷūri Gōvinda Kavi (Critical edition with translation and comments), Pub. Dhanush Infotech, Prasad Printing Press, Vishakapatnam, 2008.
12. Ed. M.S. Ramaswami Aiyar, Rāmāmātya's Svaramēlakalānidhi (A work on Music), The Annamalai University, 1932.
13. Ed. Mudikondan Venkatarama Aiyar & R. Visvanathaiyar, Mahābharata Chūḍāmaṇi Vol. 2 - Chapter Four – Saṅgītādi Rāga Mēḷa Lakṣaṇam, Mahāmahopādhyāya Doctor V. Swaminathaiyar Library, Madras, 1955.
14. Ed. N. G. Ratanajanakar & G. G. Barve, Rāgamālā of Puṇḍarīkaviṭṭhala, Pub. Bhalchandra Sitaram Sukthakar, Nirnaya-sagar Press, Bombay, 1914.
15. Ed. P.S. Sundaram Aiyar & S. Subrahmanya Sastri, The Saṅgīta Sudhā of King Raghunātha of Tanjore, The Music Academy, Madras, 1940.

16. Ed. & Pub. Jibananda Vidyasagara, Sangit Parijata – A treatise on Ancient Hindu Music by Ahobala, Saraswati press, Calcutta, 1884.
17. Ed. & Pub. R. S. Gondhalekar, Saṅgīta pārijāta of Ahōbala, Pune, 1897.
18. Ed. S. Subrahmanya Sastri, Rāgavibodha of Somātha, Adyar Library, Madras, 1945.
19. Ed. S. Subrahmanya Sastri, T. V. Subba Rao & T. L. Venkatarama Aiyar, The Chaturdandi Prakasika of Sri Venkatamakhin of Tanjore - Part 1, The Music Academy, Madras, 1934.
20. Ed. S. Seetha, Rāga Lakṣaṇamu of Śāha Mahārāja, Brhaddhvani, Madras, 1990.
21. Ed. S. Subrahmanya Sastri, T. V. Subba Rao and T.L. Venkatarama Aiyar, Rāgalakṣaṇam of Muddu Veṅkaṭamakhī – printed as an Appendix to the Chaturdandi Prakasika of Venkatamakhin of Tanjore, The Music Academy, Madras, 1934.
22. Ed. S. Subrahmanya Sastri, Saṅgītasārāmṛtam of Tulajēndra Bhūpāla, The Music Academy, Madras, 1942.
23. Ed. S. Subrahmanya Sastri, The Saṅgraha-Cūḍā-Maṇi of Govinda and The Bāhattara-Meḷa-Kartā of Veṅkaṭa-Kavi, The Adyar Library, Madras, 1938.
24. Ed. T.V. Subba Rao, Raga Tala Cintamani, Government Oriental Manuscripts Library, Madras, 1952.
25. Ed. Vibhukumar S. Desai, Rāgatattvavibodha – A work on Indian Music, Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, 1956.
26. Subbarāma Dīkṣita, Saṅgīta Sampradāya Pradarśini, Vidya Vilasini Press, Ettayapuram, 1904.
27. Narayanaswami P. P., “Caturdandi Prakasika of Venkatamakhī: Text in Devanagari & Roman, by P P Narayanaswami,” 2007
Available at <http://musicresearchlibrary.net/omeka/items/show/2275>
28. Sita S, “Ghana, naya and desya ragas”, Music conference souvenir, Music academy, (p 22-24), 1976
29. Dr. S. Sita, “The Rāga Lakshana Manuscript of Śāhaji Maharaja of Tanjāvur”, The Journal of Madras Music Academy, Vol LIV, pg (140-181), 1983